

Original Articles.

THE AMERICAN PEDIATRIC SOCIETY'S COLLECTIVE INVESTIGATION ON INFANTILE SCURVY IN NORTH AMERICA.¹

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THE subject of infantile scurvy has so recently come into prominence, and still presents so many mooted questions, especially regarding its etiology, that it was the decision of the American Pediatric Society a year ago to undertake a collective investigation of the matter, based upon the cases occurring in America. This seemed particularly needed, as no other such study upon a large number of cases has yet been made in any country.

The committee, which is now making its report, was accordingly appointed. It has been diligently at work during nearly a year, and has used every means in its power to reach reports of cases of the disease. A list as accurate as possible was prepared of all the medical journals of North America, and a notice of the proposed investigation was sent to each, inviting correspondence on the part of all readers. Letters were sent to the secretaries of the country societies in a large number of the States of the Union, requesting that notice be given at the meetings. Letters were also addressed to the professors of diseases of children in all the regular medical colleges of the United States. The "Index Medicus" was searched for the names of those who had published reports of cases, and letters were addressed to all of them, as indeed to all physicians of whom even the rumor had come of probable cases under their charge. Circulars were printed containing questions to be answered, and were sent to all the members of the American Pediatric Society, to all physicians applying for them, and finally wherever there seemed any chance of getting a response.

The questions contained in the circular requested information on the following points: Whether the case was seen in hospital or private practice; the race, sex, and age; the hygienic surroundings, family history, and previous illnesses; full details of feeding from birth, and the influence which the food appeared to have had upon the development of the disease; the symptoms in detail, with special reference to pain and its location, apparent paralysis or inability to move, swellings, fractures, hemorrhages, the condition of the gums, the presence of fever, the condition of the urine and bowels, the presence of anemia or malnutrition and of rickets or any other complicating diseases, and the character of the first symptom to develop; the treatment in detail, with duration of illness, and the time before decided improvement was discovered; the direct cause of death in fatal cases, and the *post-mortem* findings; and finally, whether the case had been published previously.

The committee has been surprised and pleased at the large number of replies received. There are other cases of which it has knowledge of which no reports could be obtained, and undoubtedly many more whose existence was not discovered. But in all the committee has collected 379 cases seen by 138 observers. Some of the cases are very incompletely reported, but in the majority of instances the answers

are for the most part satisfactory. No cases needed to be excluded as instances of mistaken diagnosis, although a very few were somewhat doubtful.

The topics covered by the questions can best be taken up for the most part seriatim, stating merely what the reports state, without vouching for the correctness of opinions.

RACE.—The race to which the subjects of the disease belong is stated in 372 cases. It is not given with definiteness sufficiently often to allow of an analysis further than to say that there were 367 white, 4 black, and 1 Chinese.

SEX.—Sex shows out of 372 cases, 189 male, that is, 51 per cent.; and 183 female, that is, 49 per cent.; a difference not decided enough to indicate that sex is an etiological factor. In the remaining cases the sex is not mentioned.

AGE.—Age is a very important matter. Although strictly speaking, the age of the cases of infantile scurvy should be limited to those under two years, the committee has ventured to include a few in children slightly or decidedly older than this; since the etiology and symptoms are not different in any respect. Question IV on the circular reads, "Age when Seen with Scurvy," while XIV reads, "Duration of Illness before Treatment was Commenced." By combining the answers to these two questions, the age at which the illness developed could be determined in most instances. Reliable information was given in 359 cases; in the remaining number the age was unknown or was not stated. The accompanying tabular arrangement shows the number of cases developing at different ages:

AGE WHEN SCURVY DEVELOPED.

Age.	Cases.	Per ct.	Age.	Cases.	Per ct.
3 wks.	1	.27	16 mos.	7	1.70
13 mos.	1	.27	17 "	6	1.67
2 "	3	.83	18 "	7	1.70
3 "	2	.55	19 "	4	1.11
4 "	9	2.50	20 "	2	.55
5 "	5	1.40	22 "	1	.27
6 "	13	3.62	23 "	1	.27
7 "	33	9.19	2 yrs.	2	.55
8 "	41	11.42	2 yrs., 3 mos.	1	.27
9 "	47	13.09	2 " 6 "	1	.27
10 "	51	14.20	2 " 7 "	1	.27
11 "	26	7.24	2 " 8 "	1	.27
12 "	25	7.00	3 " 6 "	1	.27
13 "	25	7.00	4 " 2 "	1	.27
14 "	22	6.12	6 "	1	.27
15 "	17	4.73	9 "	1	.27

It will be seen that the disease is most apt to develop between the ages of seven and fourteen months, inclusive. The youngest case was that reported by Dr. A. Matheson of Neillville, Wis. This was a child of four weeks who had already been ill five days when first seen. The child was fed at the breast. Its hygienic surroundings were poor. The disease exhibited perfectly typical symptoms and ended fatally.

The oldest child, reported by Dr. J. H. Fruitnight, was one of nine years, and was also a typical case, rapidly recovering under dietetic treatment. The cause appeared to be improper diet.

SOCIAL POSITION.—Of 379 cases it is interesting to note that 83 per cent. occurred in private practice, and only 17 per cent. in hospital practice. Although no absolute class distinctions can be based on these figures, yet they point very positively to the greater tendency of the disease to occur among the rich or the well-to-do. This tendency is still further illustrated by the statements of the writers regarding the *hygienic surroundings* of the cases. In 303 cases these are described as good, and often the statement is volun-

¹ Reported at the Tenth Annual Meeting, Cincinnati, June 2, 1898.

teered that they were of the very best. In five they were doubtful, and in only 40 are they described as bad. The figures of the report would therefore seem to indicate that the influence of bad hygienic conditions upon the etiology of the disease is extremely limited.

PREVIOUS HEALTH.—Out of 285 cases suitable for study, it is distinctly stated in 167 that the previous health had been good. In 118 the child had suffered from various diseased conditions, which may be enumerated as follows:

Bronchitis, 5; chicken-pox, 1; constipation, 1; convulsions, 3; cretinism, 1; diarrheal conditions, 45; eczema, 1; furunculosis, 1; indigestion, 22; influenza, 6; malaria, 1; measles, 7; pneumonia, 5; rheumatism, 1; scurvy (previous attack), 1; scrofulous diathesis, 1; typhoid fever, 1; whooping cough, 2.

It is evident that the occurrence of most of these diseases can only be considered as accidental. There is a striking preponderance of instances of digestive disturbance. This probably is an indication that the faulty diet which occasioned the scurvy produced the indigestion also. It is no proof that the digestive disease itself bore any etiological relation to the constitutional affection. This is clearly the view of the correspondents, for, in answer to the question of the circular, a belief in any other cause than diet is expressed in only 24 instances.

Rickets, anemia, and malnutrition are not mentioned in the foregoing list. They will be referred to later.

Attention may be called to the instance of a second attack of scurvy reported by Dr. L. E. Holt. The child was eighteen months of age at the time of the second attack, the previous one having developed four months before. The first attack followed the use of Mellin's food and sterilized milk. Recovery followed in a week upon a diet of sterilized milk and beef juice, no fruit juice being given. The second attack followed the use of Reed & Carnrick's soluble food. The patient in this attack was in a wretched condition and died in eight days.

The case of scurvy developing in a cretin, reported by Dr. A. Caillé, is also interesting. The child was a typical cretin of fourteen months. Scurvy followed the use of condensed milk. Recovery was very prompt under the administration of sterilized milk, fruit juice and cereals.

FAMILY HISTORY.—This, too, appears to exert little or no influence. In 129 cases the family history is stated to have been good, and in 97 it is negative. In 74 the following diseases are mentioned in the family:

Alcoholism, 2; anemia, 2; asthma, 1; carcinoma, 1; caries of spine, 1; diarrhea, 1; eczema, 1; gout, 2; neurotic tendency, 6; paresis, 1; pneumonia, 1; rheumatism, 16; sciatica, 1; scurvy, 1; syphilis, 7; tuberculosis, 29; uricacidemia, 1.

DIET.—The most important etiological factor, according to general opinion, is a dietetic one. Consequently, the committee has paid particular attention to this point. When correspondents did not make the matter quite clear in their answers, personal letters were addressed to them, asking for further information. A large number of such letters have been written, and replies received in most instances. Full details were asked regarding diet from birth onward, and the question of food used at the time the scurvy developed, or so shortly before that it might seem to

be associated with it, was particularly emphasized. The question was also asked, whether in the opinion of each correspondent there was reason to believe that the disease depended on the nature of the food used. An affirmative answer was received in 275 cases; negative, and the disease attributed to other causes, in 24. The committee is not in a position to judge of the correctness of this view, nor can it claim that the disease *did* arise in any instance as the result of the diet employed. It would make merely the following statements of the food employed at or shortly before the symptoms of scurvy were observed according to the reporters' replies.

Any accurate percentage analysis of the report is impossible, both because the correspondents have not always stated the exact nature of the food, and because in very many instances more than one form of food was given. Perhaps the following summary of some of the main divisions may be of value, remembering, however, that cases are repeatedly counted twice; for example, one case may be counted in the condensed milk class and again in the sterilized milk division.

FOOD USED AT OR SHORTLY BEFORE SCURVY DEVELOPED.

Number of cases in which the character of the food is specified, 356.

Food given as follows:

Breast Milk.—Alone, 10; with raw milk and amylaceæ 1; with sterilized milk and amylaceæ, 1; total, 12.

Raw Milk.—Alone, 4; with breast milk and amylaceæ, 1; total, 5.

Milk (nothing said about heating).—Alone, 8; peptonized, 4; with amylaceæ, 4; total, 16.

Sterilized Milk.—Alone, 68; with proprietary foods, 21; with amylaceæ, 8; peptonized, 10; total, 107.

Pasteurized Milk.—Alone, 16; with proprietary foods, 2; with amylaceæ, 1; peptonized, 1; total, 20.

Peptonized Milk.—Nothing further stated, 3; sterilized, 8; Pasteurized, 1; with proprietary foods, 1; with amylaceæ, 1; total, 14.

Amylaceous Food (not proprietary).—Alone, 6; with breast milk, 3; with milk, 5; with sterilized milk, 8; with Pasteurized milk, 1; with peptonized milk, 1; total, 24 (9 of these were oatmeal).

Table Food.—Nothing else mentioned, 11; with condensed milk, 1; total, 12.

Mellin's Food.—Nothing further stated, 42; with condensed milk, 22; with sterilized milk, 16; with Pasteurized milk, 2; with other proprietary food, 1; total, 83.

Malted Milk.—Nothing further stated, 44; with cream, 1; with amylaceæ, 1; with other proprietary foods, 2; total, 48.

Condensed Milk.—Alone, 32; with milk, 1; with cream, 1; with other proprietary foods, 3; with table food, 1; total, 38.

Reed & Carnrick's Soluble Food.—13.

Imperial Granum.—6.

Liebig's Food.—Alone, 1; with condensed milk 1; total, 2.

Lactated Food.—Alone, 3; with condensed milk, 1; total, 4.

Nestlé's Food.—Alone, 1; with sterilized peptonized milk, 1; total, 2.

Among other articles of diet mentioned by correspondents, each in one instance, are: Gardner's food, Robinson's barley, Ridge's food, Brush's food, animal broths, Bartlett's pepsinated food, Lactopræparata with malted milk.

There are a number of instances in which the writers mention "proprietary foods" without further desig-

nation. In all 214 cases (60 per cent.) were fed on proprietary foods.

The effect of dietetic treatment has such an important bearing upon the etiological influence of diet that the whole matter will be discussed more fully under Treatment.

SYMPTOMS.—The symptoms in infantile scurvy are so typical and well known that they would appear to need little further study. Nevertheless, the attention which has been directed to them by the questions of the circular has not been without fruit.

FIRST SYMPTOM TO DEVELOP, AND ORDER AND TIME OF OTHER SYMPTOMS.—In response to this question the answers have not been altogether satisfactory. Undoubtedly in a large number such early symptoms as anemia and malnutrition were overlooked or were not included by the readers as symptoms of the disease. Then in a large number, perhaps the majority, of cases, answers have not made it quite clear whether the correspondent intended that a certain number of symptoms developed in the order in which the names are written, or whether they all were noticed at one time. Presuming that the first is the writer's intention, we make the following statement of the first symptom seen, basing this on 327 cases. The order of symptoms is too complicated and too uncertain to warrant a statistical arrangement.

FIRST SYMPTOMS SEEN.—Pain and tenderness, 145; affection of gums, 42; interference with motion, 36; anemia, 27; cutaneous hemorrhages, 22; swellings, 16; restlessness, 6; anorexia, 5; debility, 5; diarrhea, 5; constipation, 2; hemorrhage from nose, 1; hemorrhage from mouth, 1; hemorrhage from rectum, 1; hematuria, 3; "hematoma of tongue," 1; irritability, 3; vomiting, 1; fever, 1; opisthotonos, 1; sweating, 1.

PAIN ON MOTION OR HANDLING.—Pain is clearly a very prominent symptom of the disease. Generally it is evident only when the child is moved, or tries to move itself. Sometimes it is so intense that the approach of any one to the bedside is sufficient to cause the child to scream out through fear of being touched. Pain is reported present in 314 instances. In most of the remaining, no answer was made, and it is probable that the symptom could not have been a prominent one. The locality of the pain in the cases where there were accurate details was as follows:

Legs, 120; legs and arms, 25; legs and one arm, 11; legs and body, 4; one leg, 13; one leg and one arm, 1; one arm, 1; back, 1; back and legs, 1; back and leg, 1; back and thighs, 1; thighs, 1; hips and thigh, 1; one thigh, 2; one hip, 2; knees, 1; knees and ankles, 2; knees, ankles and shoulders, 1; knees, ankles and wrists, 2; knees and arms, 1; one knee, 1; one ankle, 1; ankles, 1; ankles and feet, 1; ankles and elbows, 1; elbow, 1.

PAIN WHEN AT REST.—In 91 cases pain seems to have been present, even when the child was still; while in 134 it is definitely stated as absent under this condition.

INTERFERENCE WITH MOTION.—The symptom variously described as *paralysis*, *pseudo-paralysis* and *disability or unwillingness to move* is reported frequently. It probably depends in every instance upon pain, since there is no evidence that actual paralysis occurs in the disease. In 319 cases interference with motion of this nature existed.

Rigidity is described as present in 96 cases and absent in 106. It is due to pain in most instances, but

perhaps in others may have been occasioned or increased by the presence of swelling.

The parts of the body in which motion has been interfered with in any way in the cases reported, and the locality mentioned in detail, may be enumerated as follows:

Legs, 159; legs and arms, 55; legs and one arm, 14; legs and one hand, 2; one arm, 3; legs and thighs, 1; thighs, 3; one leg and one arm, 1; one leg, 27; one thigh, 2; hips, 1; one hip, 2; one hip and thigh, 1; one hip and knee, 3; hip, leg and shoulder, 1; hip, elbow and shoulder, 1; one knee, 4; one ankle, 2; ankles, knees, hand and wrist, 1.

POSITION OF THE LIMBS.—To a question regarding the position of the limbs, about which Barlowe speaks so definitely, there have been replies in 205 cases. In 17 of these the position was normal. In the balance we find the position of the limbs as follows:

Flexed, 152; extended, 23; flexed and abducted, 1; flexed and adducted, 1; flexed and everted, 1; abducted, 1; everted, 3; everted and extended, 2; toes extended, 1; feet extended, 3.

WEAKNESS OF THE BACK.—The occurrence of weakness of the back, a symptom which Barlowe says is marked, is mentioned as present in 97 of the cases reported to the committee and as absent in 108. In the remaining nothing is said of it.

DEPRESSION OF THE STERNUM.—This condition is likewise emphasized by Barlowe as being sometimes striking and characteristic. It is mentioned in 34 cases, but said to be absent in 170 others. It is not certain in the cases of the report how frequently the condition had developed acutely as a result of scurvy and how often it had already been produced by a previously existing rachitis.

SWELLINGS.—The effort has been made by analyzing the cases collected to determine the position of local swellings, whether these were situated in the joints or the shafts of the limbs, in the soft tissues or in the bones, and whether any redness was present. The answers are not clear in every instance, and are frequently somewhat contradictory, partly, perhaps, from failure of the observer to understand the question, and partly from lack of careful discrimination between subperiosteal and other effusions, and between effusion into a joint and that about it. The great irregularity also of the distribution of the swelling renders an accurate tabular arrangement too complicated. Remembering that in many cases more than one part of the body was involved and that the figures given do not mean that only the portion mentioned is affected in these cases, the following division may be made:

Joints (or probably oftener about joints) involved in 165 cases. Location given in 101, namely: knees, 73; ankles, 28; wrists, 12; hand, 1; elbow, 3; shoulder, 5; hip, 6.

Shafts of limbs involved in 179 cases. Location given in 123, namely: thighs, 59; legs (below knee), 61; "legs" (not further stated), 11; forearm, 5; upper arm, 4; "arm," 5; ribs, 1; scapula, 1; ilium, 1.

The gross results of the answers regarding the tissues in which the swelling occurred give: swelling in soft tissues, 97; swelling, subperiosteal, 114; swelling in both situations, 16.

In 69 cases the swollen parts were reddened also. It is stated that there was no redness in 121. A more general swelling, to be classified rather as edema, is described in 68 cases and stated to be absent in 98,

In regard to the swelling or protrusion of one or both eyes which has been described by writers, the symptom is said to have been absent in 110 cases and is reported present in 49. In nine of these swelling only is mentioned, in 18 protrusion only, and in 22 both are referred to.

GUMS.—The condition of the gums and mouth is one of extreme interest. In 16 cases it is distinctly stated that the gums were entirely unaffected, while in 313 they were diseased. The degree of involvement varies from slight swelling to great sponginess and even ulceration. The degree and form of the affection in the cases suitable for study may be seen in the following table:

Swelling: absent, 14; present, 293.
Sponginess: absent, 27; present, 249.
Discoloration: absent, 23; present, 259.
Bleeding: absent, 64; present, 188.
Ulceration: absent, 101; present, 91.

The relation of the affection of the gums to the presence of teeth is of much interest. In nearly all the cases of scurvy in this report teeth were present, but what influence this has is not quite clear, since experience teaches that curiously it is usually the gums of the upper jaw which are most affected, although the lower teeth naturally are the first cut. Statistics on the portion of the gums involved were not furnished sufficiently to allow of conclusions; but regarding the teeth it is to be noted that of 359 cases suitable for comparison, teeth had already appeared in 314 instances, that is, 87.5 per cent.; while in only 45 cases, that is, 12.5 per cent., were there no teeth. In studying more carefully these 45 cases of scurvy without teeth, we may make the following analysis:

No teeth: gums normal, 21 cases.
No teeth: gums affected, 24 cases.

The conditions present in the latter group were as follows:

Swelling, 19 cases; sponginess, 14 cases; bleeding, 5 cases; discoloration, 17 cases; ulceration, 4 cases.

This is a proof that affection of the gums may occur equally well when there are no teeth as when teeth have developed. The fact that in the great majority of cases of infantile scurvy the presence of teeth and the affection of the gums is associated depends merely on the fact that the disease generally develops at an age when teeth naturally have been cut.

CUTANEOUS HEMORRHAGES.—These have occurred with frequency in the cases reported. Accurate data are given in 353 cases. Of these, cutaneous hemorrhage is reported present in 182 and absent in 171. There is much doubt about the accuracy of the writers in their classification of the hemorrhages according to size, and to the proper use by them of the descriptive names employed, inasmuch as the question on this point did not specify clearly. In 99 instances the presence of "ecchymoses" is mentioned. In 83 "purpuric eruption" is reported and in 37 "petechiæ." In 13 the nature of the lesion is not specified.

HEMORRHAGE FROM MUCOUS MEMBRANES.—Data are available in 361 cases. Of these there were no hemorrhages from any mucous membrane in 196, while in 164 they occurred. In 93 cases there was hemorrhage from the mouth. This includes the cases where bleeding from the gums is described by writers. In 33 cases there was bleeding from the nose; in 2

from the stomach, and in 37 from the bowels. Cases of hematuria are not included here, and will be referred to later.

FRACTURES.—Fractures in infantile scurvy are usually separations of the epiphyses merely. Even this would seem to be rare, for fracture of any kind is mentioned in only 9 of our cases. In 342 it is distinctly stated to have been absent, and in the remaining the question is not answered.

FEVER.—Probably in the majority of the cases of the disease upon which this report is based no temperature record has been made. In 93 cases it is stated that there was no fever; in 182 it was present and in the remaining no answer is given. In the cases where present it is described as slight in 116 instances, moderate in 23, high in 8, and irregular in 6. Clearly, fever is not a prominent symptom of the disease, and probably often, when present, depends on accidental causes.

BOWEL MOVEMENTS.—The following conditions are mentioned: bowels regular, 74; bowels irregular, 15; constipation, 126; diarrhea, 65; bloody diarrhea, 12.

URINE.—Judging from the number of instances in which no answers have been returned, no examination of the urine has been made in most of the cases. It is reported as examined for albumin in 163 cases; in 33 of these albuminuria is reported and in 130 it was absent. Tube casts were present in 13 instances, absent in 13, and no observation reported in the others.

Properly speaking the occurrence of hematuria should be discussed under the title of hemorrhage. It is mentioned as present in 22 cases only. Of other abnormal conditions of the urine the following may be mentioned: Urine very acid, 1; urine scanty, 9; urine suppressed, 1; urine increased in quantity, 3; glycosuria, 1; hemoglobinuria, 1; pus (from cystitis), 1; phosphates increased, 1; chlorides increased, 1.

ANEMIA, MALNUTRITION.—These conditions, already referred to as often the earliest symptoms of infantile scurvy, may have been the first evidences of the disease in many of the cases on which this report is based. In other cases they must be regarded as complicating affections only. Answers are not full enough to allow of satisfactory conclusions on this point.

Anemia is said to have been present in 254 cases, as follows: anemia present (without specifying degree), 47; slight, 66; moderate, 32; marked, 109.

Blood examinations were made in 15 cases, and the conditions noted as follows: The percentage of hemoglobin was much reduced in all the cases, 8 in number, in which an examination was made, some being as low as 35 per cent. Of the seven cases in which the red blood corpuscles were counted, all showed a reduction except 2. In these 2 the number was normal or nearly so, but the hemoglobin was 50 and 35 per cent., respectively. Leucocytosis was present in 5 cases. Poikilocytosis in 2. In only one instance was there a differential count of the leucocytes made.

Of 217 cases in which the question is answered, emaciation is recorded in 167 and is said to have been absent in 50.

Malnutrition was observed in 178 cases out of 216, in which replies were made as follows; malnutrition present (without specifying degree), 108; slight, 20; moderate, 7; marked, 43.

RICKETS.—Infantile scurvy has so often been described as "scurvy rickets" and "acute rickets," that the investigation of the actual relationship of the two

diseases was one of the matters to which the committee directed especial attention. The questions upon the circular read as follows: (a) "Any symptoms of rickets present? (b) Slight or well marked? (c) What relation in time of development did they bear to the scurvy?" Satisfactory answers were received in 340 cases; in 152 of these (45 per cent.) there were symptoms of rickets present, slight in 72, marked in 64, and the degree not mentioned in 16. In the remaining cases (55 per cent.) rickets is definitely stated to have been absent. With regard to the relation in time of development, it is stated in 50 cases that the rickets was first present; in 14 that it developed with the scurvy, and in 2 after it. There does not seem to be evidence as far as this investigation teaches that the association of rickets and scurvy is at all intimate. Very possibly the same defect in diet which produced the one produced the other also, but the rapid recovery under treatment which the scurvy underwent did not apply to the rickets. This seems to indicate only accidental association of the two diseases; certainly not any causal relation between them.

OTHER COMPLICATING CONDITIONS.—A variety of affections are mentioned complicating scurvy in a number of cases as follows:

Bronchitis, 5; cretinism, 1; enlargement of inguinal glands, 1; "cerebral symptoms," 1; convulsions, 1; pneumonia, 2; boils, 1; irritability, 1; vomiting, 4; eczema, 2; enuresis, 1; sweating of the head, 1; tympanites, 1; caput medusæ, 1; diaphoresis, 1; pertussis, 2; insomnia, 1; anorexia, 2; post nasal discharge, 1; measles, 1; restlessness, 1; phimosis, 1; indigestion, 2; laryngismus stridulus, 1; cystitis, 1.

(To be continued.)

MAJOR AMPUTATIONS AT THE MASSACHUSETTS GENERAL HOSPITAL.

A STUDY OF THE MORTALITY FROM 1822 TO 1896.

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THE major amputations done at the Massachusetts General Hospital from 1822 to 1870 were compiled by Dr. James R. Chadwick in elaborate and carefully prepared tables, and were published in May, 1871.

It was found that during the first period, the pre-antiseptic period, 699 amputations of the limbs had been done. The mortality percentage for this period has been recorded in the table following:

MORTALITY PERCENTAGES FOR THE FIRST PERIOD, 1822-1870.

1. Amputation at the Shoulder-Joint.		
Traumatic, primary		53.33
Pathological		27.27
2. Amputation of the Arm.		
Traumatic, primary		19.44
Traumatic, secondary		12.50
Pathological		12.50
3. Amputation of the Forearm.		
Traumatic, primary		24.13
Traumatic, secondary		14.81
Pathological		14.81
4. Amputation of the Thigh.		
Traumatic, primary		42.37
Traumatic, secondary		60.00
Pathological		20.98
5. Amputation at the Knee-Joint.		
Traumatic, primary		60.00
Traumatic, secondary		60.00
Pathological		36.36
6. Amputation of the Leg.		
Traumatic, primary		34.37
Traumatic, secondary		36.41
Pathological		12.60

At the Massachusetts General Hospital, between the years 1870 and 1890, the second period, for a space of twenty years 657 major amputations have been performed.

Through imperfections in the records two cases are not complete enough to include in this report.

The anatomical groups of cases are subdivided into those cases operated upon for disease and for traumatism, that is, pathological and traumatic groups, and this last group is further divided into primary and secondary classes, according as the amputation was done within or after the twenty-four hours immediately following the accident.

After a careful analysis of these groups of cases, I have determined the average mortality in each, and the causes of death in so far as the records would allow.

There was one amputation at the hip-joint during this period, with recovery. There has been one amputation at the elbow-joint, which died. There have been four amputations at the ankle-joint and four amputations at the wrist-joint, with no mortality. There have been 38 cases of partial amputation of the foot. There have been 77 amputations of fingers and toes.

These cases mentioned above are not included in the estimates of mortality of the major amputations given below.

AMPUTATIONS AT THE SHOULDER-JOINT.

Traumatic, Primary.—Recovered, 7 cases; died, 7; total, 14. Mortality, 50 per cent. Causes of death: from shock, 6 cases; internal hemorrhage, 1. The accidents necessitating these amputations were crushes, which in almost every instance caused extensive injury to the parts adjacent to the shoulder and arm; hence the great shock, which caused death.

Pathological.—Recovered, 3 cases; died, 0; total, 3.

AMPUTATIONS OF THE UPPER ARM.

Traumatic, Primary.—Recovered, 36 cases; died, 5; total, 41. Mortality, 12.19 per cent. Causes of death: from shock, 4 cases; hemorrhage, 1.

Pathological.—Recovered, 26 cases; died, 5; total, 31. Mortality, 16.12 per cent. Causes of death: from shock, 3 cases; record incomplete, 2.

AMPUTATIONS OF THE FOREARM.

Traumatic, Primary.—Recovered, 37 cases; died, 11; total, 48. Mortality, 22.99 per cent. Causes of death: from shock, 5 cases; secondary hemorrhage, 2; ether, 1 (the autopsy showed no lesion to account for death); sepsis, 2; fracture of base of the skull, 1.

Pathological.—Recovered, 22 cases; died, 3; total, 25. Mortality, 14 per cent. Causes of death: tetanus, 2 cases; uremia, 1.

AMPUTATIONS OF THE LEG.

Traumatic, Primary.—Recovered, 86 cases; died, 33; total, 119. Mortality, 27.73 per cent. Causes of death: from delirium tremens, 1 case; secondary hemorrhage, 1 case in 1877; fat embolus, 1; internal injuries, 1; carbolic-acid poisoning, 1; shock, 17; sepsis, 11 (two of these cases became septic from gangrene of the part. Eighty-eight of these cases were railroad accidents, and of these 88 cases, 23 died.

Traumatic, Secondary.—Recovered, 22 cases; died, 6; total, 28. Mortality, 21.43 per cent. Causes of death: from sepsis 4 cases; shock, 2.

Pathological.—Recovered, 100 cases; died, 16; total, 116. Mortality, 13.78 per cent. Six of these deaths occurred previous to 1879, and were due to sepsis. Seven of these deaths occurred in elderly people, the amputation

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